

Reprocessing and Quality Control of Heritage Third Party Optical Earth Observation Missions

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An overview of the Quality Control (QC) work undertaken for heritage optical missions through the European Space Agency (ESA) IDEAS-QA4EO (Instrument Data quality Evaluation and Analysis Service - Quality Assurance for Earth Observation) service is provided. As an example, the challenges and successes faced when reprocessing the Japanese Marine Observation Satellites (MOS-1 and -1b), which operated in the 1980s and 90s, are described. The reprocessing of such missions often requires the development of a new processor, and the input ancillary as well as image source data needs to be investigated/tested to ensure that the highest quality reprocessed dataset is generated. These activities support the preservation of such datasets and their (re-)use, which becomes particularly important for climate change impact studies where long time-series datasets are needed.

Introduction

The ESA is responsible for the reprocessing and distribution of Earth Observation (EO) data from both their own satellite missions and the Third Party Missions (TPM) programme¹. The TPM programme consists of around 50 satellite missions, including datasets where the EO data was received at ESA ground stations, with datasets collected from the 1970s onwards.

ESA supported missions that have been inactive for over 5 years are covered via ESA's Heritage Space Programme². Support for the reprocessing activities of such missions is provided by the IDEAS-QA4EO service, whose responsibilities include the iterative QC of test datasets generated by the Instrument Processing Facilities (IPF) and then, finally, the generated full dataset. These historical datasets can be extremely valuable as they may have been collected when limited satellites were in orbit or offer unique capabilities. An overarching aim is to allow the historical data to be accessible by the scientific community in a recognisable file format, with metadata and documentation supporting an understanding of known limitations and anomalies.

Difficulties can be faced in bringing historical datasets up to the standards of modern missions. Reprocessing challenges occur as documentation may be limited, and the Level 0 datasets (the rawest form of the data archived) may not have associated with it all the ancillary data needed. Also, the reprocessing activities consider what would make the dataset most useful to end users. This involves choosing an appropriate output format and including metadata files that allow quick access to information to support automated and/or cloud-based processing.

¹ <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/missions/third-party-missions>

² <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/what-are-heritage-missions->

Methodology for the MOS-1 and -b Reprocessing

Datasets from the MOS-1 and -1b National Space Development Agency of Japan (NASDA) satellites were received by the ESA during the 1980s and 90s – the missions also carried a two-channel Microwave Scanning Radiometer (MSR), but that data was not the focus of this activity.

Figure 1 shows example products from Multispectral Electronic Self-Scanning Radiometer (MESSR) and Visible and Thermal Infrared Radiometer (VTIR). MESSR is like the data from the USGS Landsat missions with a swath width of 100 km, 50 m spatial resolution, and four multispectral bands in the blue, green, red, and Near InfraRed (NIR). VTIR is like the data from the NOAA AVHRR missions with a 1500 km swath width, visible band at 900 m resolution, and three NIR to thermal IR bands at 1.1 km resolution. The MOS satellites orbited at an altitude of around 900 km with a revisit period of 17 days. When both operated, this reduced to half as they were in the same orbit but separated by 180 degrees. For MESSR, the orbit is split into a series of scenes, while for VTIR the orbit is covered by a single scene.

Figure 1: Example products from MESSR and VTIR shown for Europe.

ESA has developed, through Exprivia, an IPF for MOS data for both MESSR and VTIR products. The aim of the new processor, and hence reprocessed dataset, was to allow the MESSR and VTIR data from these historical missions to be accessible by the scientific community in GeoTIFF format. The data is held within a Standard Archive Format for Europe (SAFE)³ compliant ZIP file containing individual GeoTIFF files for each band, KML and PNG files for visualisation, plus XML metadata and CSV quality report files.

The data is geometrically, but not terrain, corrected with Ground Control Points (GCPs) when there's sufficient visibility for MESSR. If insufficient GCPs are matched, then GES (Geocoded Ellipsoid System

³ <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/safe-the-standard-archive-format-for-europe>

Corrected) rather than GEC (Geocoded Ellipsoid GCP Corrected) data is generated for MESSR. The VTIR data is always GES, as GCPs are not used.

The reprocessing has required a complicated processing setup as the two optical instruments need to be processed in a specific order - the geolocation information is improved by processing the MESSR, which is then used for the VTIR. In addition, to account for the needed Time Correlation (TC) information, the Level 0 dataset has been processed twice: the first time, what we call “forward processing”, where the complete missions were processed from the beginning to the end of the dataset. After this, the new TC files generated by the IPF are more precise than those originally provided by ESA. Therefore, the “backward processing” is then performed from the mission end to the beginning, allowing the IPF to process data with more accurate geolocation.

In terms of a summary of the QC results, for the backward processing there was an increase in the number and percentage of GEC products (by 3%) compared to the forward processing, even if the total number of scenes was 263 118, compared to 264 453 for the forward processing, so a reduction of just over ~1 300 scenes. These scene numbers do not represent the complete archive as some missing Level 1 products were identified due to too large a gap in the TC file coverage, and so further reprocessing activities are being undertaken to generate those products.

In addition, both datasets have a limited radiometric correction with Digital Numbers (DNs) generated. So, the ESA-funded Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot (EDAP) undertook a preliminary cross-comparison of the MESSR data to Landsat-5 Thematic Mapper data to see if a conversion to radiometric units is possible (Lavender 2022); see Figure 2 for some preliminary results. Historically, previous processors operated by NASDA (Henry and Begni 1989) and Canada (Robert and Wiebe, 1989) have undertaken these cross-mission comparisons to create MESSR and VTIR data in radiometric units. However, work is needed to understand if the required ancillary data is available and can be extracted from the ESA archive, so the first release of the datasets will not be radiometrically corrected.

Figure 2: Regression between the MOS (MESSR) digital numbers and Landsat-5 TM radiance data for band 1/2 and 2/3 combinations; from Lavender (2022).

Discussion and Conclusions

As outlined for the MOS missions, the reprocessing of heritage optical missions often requires the development of a new processor. This processor development requires gathering information from multiple sources, including scanned paper-based versions of technical documents and published papers, and an iterative process to test the new processor before the full reprocessing occurs. The reprocessing needs not only the Level 0 imagery source data but also ancillary sources of information that support the accurate geometric registration and radiometric calibration. Knowledge of these ancillary sources may have been lost over time, so the team must rediscover the setup needed to generate the highest quality dataset.

With the increased popularity of Analysis Ready Data (ARD), which provides data in a form that allows immediate analysis with a minimum of additional user effort, reprocessing campaigns are also considering whether datasets can be processed to Level 2 and stored to comply with the CEOS ARD specifications (<https://ceos.org/ard/>). For the MOS datasets, the next step would be to work on the radiometric calibration as part of further IPF improvements, and then the development of an ARD dataset could be considered.

References

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